

A New Method to Characterize Stiffness Development in Polymers

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Abstract

The polymer stiffness development during a cure cycle was determined by combining results obtained from a cure-induced stress tests (CIST) on single fiber carbon/ 3501-6 epoxy composites, and volumetric dilatometry experiments on neat 3501-6 polymer samples. The stiffness results were compared with by independent stiffness measurements using three-point flexure tests on of fully and partially cured samples. The comparison showed that the CIST experiment provides a simple procedure to determine the polymer stiffness development during a given cure cycle.

KEY WORDS: Residual Stress, Polymer Volume Change, Resin Cure

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1. INTRODUCTION

As the matrix cures and its volume changes. The polymer volume change will apply cure induced stresses on the embedded fiber, and hence the reading at the load cell will

change. It can be shown using simple mechanics of material principles that any change in the cure-induced stress during a given time interval of a cure cycle will depend on three factors – the amount of the polymer volume change, instantaneous stiffness of the polymer, and polymer stress relaxation characteristics during that time interval of the cure cycle. For example, during the early part of a cure cycle when polymer is only partially cured and its stiffness is low, a given volume change of the polymer is not expected to produce large fiber stresses. Moreover, most of these stresses will quickly decay due to polymer stress relaxation. Whereas, towards the later part of a cure cycle when the polymer is close to a complete cure and its stiffness is fully developed, even a small volume change in polymer is expected to produce a relatively large fiber stress. In addition, these stresses may not be readily relaxed. Coupling between volume change and cure-induced stresses has been shown extensively through investigations of in-cure internal stresses [1-15]. Work has also been done to determine the effect of cure cycle on residual stresses [6], in which development of volume change, viscosity, and stresses are investigated for various cure cycles.

Studies of the static and dynamic characteristics of epoxy and acrylate resins during cure [7,8,9] have given insight into the development of elastic and viscoelastic properties. The magnitude of in-cure stress buildup was seen to vary by as much as a factor of 30 for various material types. In order to quantify viscoelasticity, dynamic shear modulus was measured at various frequencies. From dynamic storage modulus data at various frequencies correlated with shrinkage data, the development of relaxation modulus with respect to progression of cure was calculated. In the current study, a procedure based on the fiber load change during cure was used to characterize fiber stress relaxation and stiffness development during various cure cycles

In studies done with composite laminates to monitor the modulus development with degree of cure [10,11], the matrix dominated transverse modulus of unidirectional composite laminate was shown to be sensitive to degree of cure. The trends of modulus development with degree of cure reported in refs. 10 and 11 are similar to those obtained from CIST

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 In-Cure Volume Change Measurement

Total volume changes were measured directly using a volumetric dilatometer. The volumetric dilatometer used was the Gnomix Research PVT Apparatus. This instrument yields measurements of total sample volume change during a given cure cycle. The details of the experimental setup and procedure are explained in [12].

2.2 In-Cure Stress Testing

The *cure-induced stress test* (CIST) was used to measure the fiber stresses developed during cure of a polymer composite due to volume changes. In the CIST setup a polymer is cured around a given length of pretensioned fiber. Once the polymer develops sufficient stiffness, polymer expansions and contractions cause changes in the fiber tension, which can be measured by a load cell attached to the fiber ends. The detailed description and schematic of this procedure and test setup can be found in ref. 1-6.

3. APPROACH

The current study describes a simple method to determine the polymer stiffness development as it cures. Although the approach is developed for various isothermal cure cycles, the procedure can be applied to any cure cycle. As the polymer cross-linking progresses during cure, its stiffness changes from a very low value to that of a fully cured polymer. During the early stages of a cure cycle when the resin is unreacted and stiffness is low, the developed fiber stresses will be instantly relaxed due to short stress relaxation times. Whereas, during the later part of a cure cycle as the monomers crosslink, the fiber stresses resulting from the polymer volumetric changes may not be relaxed.

The procedure to determine the qualitative behavior of stiffness during a given cure cycle involved both the results from the volumetric dilatometer and the CIST. First, the polymer volume change was measured during three isothermal cure cycle (126°C, 136°C and 169°C). Isothermal cure cycles were chosen in this study because there is no temperature change; hence all the polymer volume change is due only to cure shrinkage. Secondly, CIST experiments were performed on following systems:

- a) The 3501-epoxy was cured around a pretensioned carbon fiber and the change in fiber tension was recorded for various cure cycles.
- b) The 3501-epoxy was cured around embedded fibers Teflon coated pre-tensioned carbon fibers. The change in fiber tension was recorded for various cure cycles. The purpose of using Teflon coated fibers was to weaken the fiber-matrix interface bond and thus determine the effect of fiber/matrix adhesion on the recorded data.

- c) CIST experiments on single fiber carbon/3501 epoxy composites for the same three isothermal cure temperatures (i.e. 126°C, 136°C and 169°C).

A comparison of results for parts (a) and (b) is shown in Figure 2. As can be seen from this figure that both the Teflon coated and uncoated fibers produce identical fiber tension results. This implies that stresses being transferred are lower than those required to cause slip at the interface. The interface strength builds up as the polymer cures. During the early part of the cure cycle when interface is weak and not fully developed, the polymer stiffness is low and as a result the stresses being transferred are also low. Thus, in light of the results shown in Figure 2 it is reasonable to assume that stresses produced are not large enough to cause slip at the interface during the entire cure cycle.

Figure 2. A comparison of CIST results from using Uncoated and Teflon coated fibers. The weakening of interface due to Teflon coating does not affect the load readings in the CIST experiments.

A change in fiber tension that occurs during the CIST depends mostly on two factors - polymer volume change and polymer stiffness. The polymer volume change that occurs during the beginning of the cure cycle produces only a small change in fiber tension because of the low polymer stiffness. Whereas, the same amount of polymer volume change occurring towards the later part of the cure cycle when polymer stiffness is high will produce a larger fiber load change. One can therefore see the correlation between the measured load change in the fiber and the instantaneous stiffness of the polymer.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Correlation between Fiber Tension and Volume Change

Figure 3a-c shows the volume change and fiber tension change curves during three different isothermal cure cycles. The volume and tension data are taken from the volumetric dilatometer and the CIST, respectively.

The linear strain in the polymer can be deduced from the total volume change data using the following equations:

$$\varepsilon_{vol} = \frac{\Delta v}{v_o} \text{-----(1)}$$

$$\varepsilon = (1 + \varepsilon_{vol})^{1/3} - 1 \text{----- (2)}$$

where Δv is change in specific volume, v_o is original specific volume (at room temperature before cure), ε_{vol} is volumetric strain, and ε is linear strain.

Figure 4a-c shows the relationship between fiber tension versus polymer strain for isothermal cure cycles of 126, 136, and 169 °C. It should be noted that time actually progresses from right to left in these figures since the strain is decreasing as the cure progresses. Towards the beginning of cure, the polymer stiffness is comparatively low in its gel-like uncured state. The strains applied by cure shrinkage do little to increase the stresses in the polymer. As cure begins to progress, the sample hardens and the shrinkage strain produces larger increase in fiber load.

The slope of the load-strain curve should be proportional to the instantaneous value of the polymer stiffness. The slope is plotted as a function of time in Figure 5. The character of the curves is reasonable given the nature of the progression of cure. As the rate of degree of cure begins to decrease upon approaching final degree of cure, the development of the stiffness begin to decrease, asymptotically approaching the polymer vitrification state. Note that in Figures 5 and 6, no stiffness values are indicated. It is purposely because the stiffness values were obtained as the slope of the load-strain curves, so the units are not congruent with those of the stiffness. What is important is the trend illustrated by this curve. The actual values of the stiffness will be obtained below by scaling these curves against the known stiffness values.

The degree of cure during the three isotherms was calculated using the cure kinetics equations described in Ref. 12. The stiffness development during cure is plotted as a function of degree of cure in Figure 6. The charts of stiffness development are seen to mimic the progression of degree of cure. This relationship is generally confirmed by Figure 6, which shows linearity between the elastic modulus and the degree of cure for 126 and 136°C isothermal cure cycles. For the 169 °C isothermal cure cycle, the elasticity development is mostly linear until when

Figure 3. Fiber tension and polymer volume changes results during three isothermal cure cycles: Top Figure – 126°C Isotherm; Middle Figure – 136°C Isotherm, and Bottom Figure – 169°C Isotherm.

Figure 4. Fiber load versus polymer linear strain for three different isothermal cure cycles. The slope of fiber tension versus strain is proportional to the polymer elasticity. A solid line indicates the curve fit. Note that the time increases from right to left on the x-axis.

Figure 5: Development of elastic modulus during isothermal cure for 3501-6. The development is seen to mimic the progression of degree of cure.

Figure 6: Development of elastic modulus during isothermal cure cycles for 3501-6. Stiffness development is largely linear with respect to degree of cure.

the cure approaches completion. The reason for this is that 169 °C cure temperature is close to the glass transition temperature (172°C) of the polymer; hence in this case the polymer is expected to reach a fully cured state. As the cure approaches completion, the rate of cure decreases. The stiffness development also mimics the same behavior.

To determine the actual stiffness values during a cure cycle, the stiffness development curves (such as shown in Figure 5) must be calibrated against known stiffness values. For this purpose, 3-point flexure experiments were conducted on several rectangular specimens (60 mm long, 10 mm wide and 2 mm deep) that were fully or partially cured at 136 and 169°C isothermal cure cycles. For the fully cured specimens, the cure duration was 180 and 480 minutes for 136°C and 169°C isothermal cure cycles, respectively. It can be seen from Figure 4 that stiffness values reach their maximum at these times. For the partially cured specimens, the cure duration was 45 minutes and 210 minutes for 136°C and 169°C isothermal cure cycles, respectively. Each flexural loading specimen was instrumented with an electrical resistance strain gage on its underside to measure the strain during loading. Specimen bending stress was calculated from the following equation:

$$\sigma = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2} \text{-----(3)}$$

where, P = applied load, L = Length between the end supports, b = specimen width, and h = specimen height. Typical plots of bending stress versus bending strain are shown in Figure 7. The bending stiffness was determined from the slope of stress- strain curves of Figure 7. The average values (of three specimens per case) bending stiffness are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Measured values of bending stiffness for partially and fully cured specimens.

	136°C Partially Cured	136°C Fully Cured	169°C Partially Cured	169°C Fully Cured
Bending Stiffness (GPa)	4.4	5.2*	3.6	5.75

*This data was used to calibrate the stiffness curve

Thus, knowing the actual bending stiffness, the stiffness versus time plot of Figure 5 can now be calibrated. The stiffness data of fully cured specimen at 136°C was used for calibrating all the stiffness curves. The calibrated curves and the data point used for calibration (solid circle) are shown in Figure 8. As can be seen that the remaining three data points (open circles) fall on their respective curves. This suggests that the procedure presented here can be used for

Figure 7: Bending stress versus bending strain curves for partially and fully cured specimens at 136°C and 169°C isothermal cure temperatures.

determining the polymer stiffness development during its cure. Although the results presented here are for isothermal cure cycles, the procedure can be applied for any cure cycle.

Figure 8. Calibrated stiffness development curves for 3501-6 epoxy during various isothermal cure cycle. The measured stiffness data (solid circle) of fully cured at 136°C was used to calibrate the entire chart. The other three measured stiffness values (open circles) fall on their respective curves.

5 SUMMARY and CONCLUSIONS

1. A procedure for measuring the polymer stiffness development during its cure has been developed. In this procedure, the cure-induced fiber load is measured in an embedded single fiber during a given cure cycle. The polymer volume change is measured for the same cure cycle using volumetric dilatometry. The polymer volume and the fiber load data are combined to generate polymer stiffness development curves during the cure.
2. The stiffness curves were calibrated by using independently measured bending stiffness data of 136°C fully cured specimens. The calibrated curves were compared with the measured stiffness data of fully and partially cured specimens cured at 136°C and 169°C. There was an excellent agreement between the measured stiffness values and the values given by the stiffness development curves.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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7. REFERENCES

1. Madhukar, M. S. , M. S. Genidy, and J.D. Russell, “A new Method to Reduce Cure-Induced Stresses in Thermoset Polymer Composites, Part I: Test Method”, to appear in Journal of Composite Materials
2. Genidy, M. S. , M. S. Madhukar, and J.D. Russell, “A new Method to Reduce Cure-Induced Stresses in Thermoset Polymer Composites, Part II: Closed Loop Feedback Control System”, to appear in Journal of Composite Materials
3. Russell, J.D., M. S. Madhukar, M. S. Genidy, and A.Y. Lee, “A new Method to Reduce Cure-Induced Stresses in Thermoset Polymer Composites, Part III: Correlating Stress History to Viscosity, Degree of Cure, and Cure Shrinkage”, to appear in Journal of Composite Materials
4. Madhukar, M.S. , M.S. Genidy, and J.D. Russell. 1999. “On Cure Induced Stresses in Low Temperature Cure Polymer Composite Materials,” Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, (18)14:1304-1321.
5. Genidy, M.S. 1999. “On the Reduction of Cure-Induced Stresses in Thermoset Polymer Composites,” Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, TN.
6. Genidy, M.S., M.S. Madhukar, J.D. Russell. 1997. “A Feedback System to Obtain an Optimum Cure Cycle for Thermoset Matrix Composites,” Proceedings of the 29th International SAMPE Conference, Orlando, Florida, 302-316.
7. Lange, J. , S. Toll, J.E. Manson, and A. Hult. 1997. “Residual Stress Build-up in Thermoset Films Cured Below Their Ultimate Glass Transition Temperature,” Polymer, vol.38, no. 4, 809-815.
8. Lange, J. , J.E. Manson, and A. Hult. 1996. “Build-up of Structure and Viscoelastic Properties in Epoxy and Acrylate Resins Cured Below Their Ultimate Glass Transition Temperature,” Polymer, vol. 37, no. 26, 5859-5868.
9. Simon, Sindee L., McKenna, Gregory B., and Sindt, Oliver, “Modeling the Evolution of the Dynamic Mechanical Properties of a Commercial Epoxy during Cure after Gelation,” Journal of Applied Polymer Science, Vol. 76 pp. 495-508 (2000)
10. White S.R. and H.T. Hahn. Nov. 1990. “Mechanical Property and Residual Stress Development During Cure of Graphite/BMI Composite”, Polymer Engineering and Science, Vol. 30, No. 22, 1465-1473.
11. Lee S.Y. and G.S. Springer. Jan. 1988. “Effects of Cure on Mechanical Properties of Composites”, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 22, 15-29.
12. Karkkainen, R.L., M.S. Madhukar, J.D. Russell, K.M. Nelson. May 21-25, 2000. “Empirical Modeling of In-Cure Volume Changes of 3501-6 Epoxy,” *Proceedings of the 45th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition – Science of Advanced Materials and Process Engineering Series*, Vol. 45, Long Beach CA, Society for the Advancement of Materials and Process Engineering, pp 123-135.

13. Yeong K. Kim and I.M Daniel, "Cure Cycle Effect on Composite Structures Manufactured by Resin Transfer Molding", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Volume 36 (14), pp 1725-1744, (2002).
14. Qi Zhu and Philippe H. Geubelle, "Dimensional Accuracy of Thermoset Composites : Shape Optimization," Volume 36 Issue 06, pp. 647-672 (2002).
15. Hubert, P., Johnston, A., Poursartip, A. and Vaziri, R., "A Two-Dimensional Finite Element Processing Model for FRP Composite Components", *Proceedings of The 10th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-10)*, Whistler, B.C., August 1995